

The Open Science Workspace for Collaborative Data-driven
Discovery

Facilitating Reproducibility

Using the CyVerse Discovery Environment (DE) for
Reproducible Computational Analysis.

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The Obvious

- Reproducibility is Crucial
- Manage Data Lifecycle
- Manage **Software Lifecycle**

Discovery Environment

Data Management: CyVerse Data Store

Managing Container & Application Life Cycle

The screenshot shows the Discovery Environment interface. At the top, there is a search bar and a navigation menu. The main content area displays the 'JupyterLab Datascience' application. Below the application name, there is a 'Version' field showing '4.0.1'. A 'Back' button is visible in the top left. The page is titled 'Analysis Info' and includes a 'Step 1: Analysis Info' section. There are input fields for 'Analysis Name *' (containing 'JupyterLab_Datascience_analysis1'), 'Comments', and 'Output Folder *' (containing '/iplant/home/nirav/analyses').

This screenshot shows the details page for the application. A red dashed box highlights the 'Version' field, which contains '4.0.1'. Below the version field, there are three navigation buttons: 'Details', 'Tool(s) used by this App', and 'Documentation'.

Powered By [CyVerse](#) repo status [Active](#) DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4540701](#)
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jupyterlab-datascience

[Project Jupyter](#) Datascience Notebook with a few added packages for use in [CyVerse Discovery Environment](#)

Jupyter Lab Datascience image built from the [Datascience Notebook](#) for [CyVerse VICE](#). Project Jupyter's base image requires a couple additional configuration files for it be compatible with CyVerse Kubernetes orchestration and iRODS data store.

harbor [passing](#) commits since v1.0.0 [89](#)

quick launch

Development

1. Use either CodeSpaces or another clean Dev Environment that you trust to clone the repository

Managing Container & Application Life Cycle (HPC)

The screenshot displays the DISCOVERY ENVIRONMENT web interface. The top navigation bar includes the logo, a search bar, and a dropdown menu for 'Apps'. The main content area shows a list of applications under the 'High-Performance Computing' category. The list is organized into columns for 'Name' and 'Type'. Each application entry includes a checkbox for selection and a red prohibition sign next to the MACS 1.4.2 application.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name ↑	Type
<input type="checkbox"/>	Index FASTA file (faidx) 0.0.0	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	InterProScan Sequence Search 5.35.74	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	InterProScan Sequence Search 5.36.75	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	InterProScan Sequence Search 5.41.78	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	InterProScan Sequence Search 5.45.80	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	InterProScan Sequence Search 5.45.80	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	InterProScan Sequence Search 5.52.86	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Kallisto Run 0.1.19	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Kallisto v0.43.0 0.43.0	HPC
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> MACS 1.4.2	HPC

Easy Access to Software

- Researchers
- Educators

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[f](#) *UNC biochemistry workshop students (Credit: Elizabeth Brunk)*

CyVerse-Powered Workshop Teaches Hundreds of UNC Students Data Science Analysis

Approximately 350 UNC undergrad workshop students learned data science analysis using Jupyter notebooks powered by CyVerse.

CyVerse Team

CyVerse Paper (2023 PLoS Comp Bio, Accepted)

Cold
Spring
Harbor
Laboratory

bioRxiv

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CyVerse: Cyberinfrastructure for Open Science

Tyson L. Swetnam, Parker B. Antin, Ryan Bartelme, Alexander Bucksch, David Camhy, Greg Chism, Illyoung Choi, Amanda M. Cooksey, Michele Cosi, Cindy Cowen, Michael Culshaw-Maurer, Robert Davey, Sean Davey, Upendra Devisetty, Tony Edgin, Andy Edmonds, Dmitry Fedorov, Jeremy Frady, John Fonner, Jeffrey K. Gillan, Iqbal Hossain, Blake Joyce, Konrad Lang, Tina Lee, Shelley Littin, Ian Mcewen, Nirav Merchant, David Micklos, Andrew Nelson, Ashley Ramsey, Sarah Roberts, Paul Sarando, Edwin Skidmore, Jawon Song, Mary Margaret Sprinkle, Sriram Srinivasan, Jonathan D. Strootman, Sarah Stryeck, Reetu Tuteja, Matthew Vaughn, Mojb Wali, Mariah Wall, Ramona Walls, Liya Wang, Todd Wickizer, Jason Williams, John Wregglesworth, Eric Lyons

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